

SMA-TB OUTCOMES AND VARIABLES ANALYSIS PLAN

Nino Gogichadze¹, Anne Ma Dyrhol-Riise², Judith Farrés¹, Jérôme Nigou³, Lilibeth Arias¹, Eleonora Vianello⁴, Chiara Sopegno¹, Kaori Fonseca¹, Noelia Alonso-Rodríguez², Nestani Tukvadze⁵, Ziyaad Waja⁶, Tumelo Moloantoa⁶, Neil Martinson⁶, Sergo Vashakidze⁵, Tom H.M. Ottenhoff⁴, Cristina Vilaplana^{1*}

1. Experimental TB Unit, Germans Trias I Pujol Research Institute & Hospital (IGTP-HUGTIP). Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona. Catalonia, Spain.
2. Oslo University Hospital, Norway.
3. Institut de Pharmacologie et de Biologie Structurale (IPBS); Centre Nationale de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS). France.
4. Leiden University Medical Center (LUMC). The Netherlands.
5. National Center for TB and Lung Diseases (NCTLD). Georgia.
6. Perinatal HIV Research Unit (PHRU), University of Witwatersrand. South Africa.

*Contact: Cristina Vilaplana, MD, PhD, Head of the Experimental TB Unit, IGTP/HUGTIP. cvilaplana@igtp.cat

In line with the European Commission’s agreement detailed in both the SMA-TB proposal and the signed Grant Agreement (GA N° 847762), the SMA-TB Consortium established a framework to assess the effectiveness of Host-Directed Therapies (HDT) when used alongside the tuberculosis (TB) Standard of Care (SoC) treatment. This evaluation goes beyond the primary endpoints of the randomised controlled trial (RCT) (NCT04575519) [1] and includes analyses of biomarkers. This document aims to give SMA-TB partners insights on the variables and outcomes to use when analysing their results.

1. Key variables and Outcomes to be used for the analysis

Key variables for TB are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Key variables in TB clinical studies.			
What do the variables assess	Variable	Meaning	When to consider
CLINICAL SEVERITY	TB Score value	Symptoms and signs scale, as higher the value, the severer the disease. The TB Score is classified as follows: Class I: ≤ 5 Class II: 6–7 Class III: ≥ 8 Decreases along the course of treatment	BL and at all time points along the treatment
	Total SGRQ score	Assess the impact of the disease on the respiratory function; decreases along the treatment. The SGRQ score ranges from 0 (best) to 100 (worst), with scores up to 7 considered to be within the healthy range.	BL and at all time points along the treatment

	Lab inflammatory parameters: Haemoglobin N/L ratio M/L ratio ESR	Presence of anaemia (low haemoglobin: less than 13,5 gm/dl in a man or less than 12,0 gm/dl in a woman) and higher inflammatory parameters are associated with more severe disease. During effective treatment, anaemia typically improves reflected by rising haemoglobin levels and inflammatory parameters decrease.	BL and at all time points along treatment
RADIOLOGICAL SEVERITY	Presence of cavities	Associated to lung damage, thus with more severe disease. Size and number of cavities are also related to severity. Cavities can evolve with time and treatment, usually reduce/disappear, even if scars can remain	BL is the most important, but also can be evaluated along the treatment (to record their evolution)
	Radiological extent of disease measured by RTBES score	Three values are available: (1) A total score, (2) A signs of activity sub-score, reflecting acute disease changes, (3) A signs of non-active findings sub-score, indicating residual lung sequelae	BL and at all time points along the treatment
MICROBIOLOGICAL SEVERITY:	AFB in sputum smear	Presence vs absence: presence of AFB in the sputum smear confirms TB, absence does not exclude TB.	BL and at all time points along treatment
	Time to stable SCC	SCC from positive to negative refers to the point during treatment when the sputum culture initially becomes negative, and this negativity is consistently sustained in subsequent sputum cultures. (To establish stable negativity, two consecutive sputum cultures from the patient must show the absence of bacilli). It can be expressed in weeks or months as Fast (≤ 8 weeks) vs Slow (>8 weeks) converters. Slow conversion reflects poor microbiological control, difficulty in clearing the infection. There are few instances where this value may not be accessible due to an inability to assess it (N/A).	a) when stable SCC is achieved and b) consequent patient's status of fast or slow converter
	Time to positivity in liquid medium culture	Expressed as days and hours. As shorter is the time to obtain a positive result the higher the bacillary load	Along treatment, several values (until the sputum culture is negative)
	Drug Susceptibility of the <i>M. tuberculosis</i> strain responsible	MDR implies more severe disease and worse outcomes.	BL
AFB: Acid fast bacilli, BL: Baseline, ESR: Erythrocyte sedimentation rate, MDR: Multi-drug resistant, M/L: Monocyte/lymphocyte ratio, N/L: Neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio, SCC: Sputum culture conversion, TB: Tuberculosis			

If treatment is effective, over time we should observe the following:

- Improvement of CLINICAL SEVERITY variables:
 - Decrease in TB score (total value) [2,3]
 - Decrease or absence of the signs and symptoms
 - Improvement of anaemia (if treatment is working anaemia should resolve)
 - Decrease in Saint George's Respiratory Questionnaire (SGRQ) [4]
 - Decrease in the inflammatory parameters: neutrophil/lymphocyte (NL) ratio, monocytes/lymphocyte (ML) ratio, erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) [5,6].
- Improvement of RADIOLOGICAL SEVERITY variables
 - Decrease in size or disappearance of cavities.
 - Decrease in radiological score (we used RTBES [7] where total and activity scores should decrease, non-activity should remain the same or increase).
- Improvement of MICROBIOLOGICAL SEVERITY variables
 - Sputum smear should become negative (these findings should be complemented with sputum culture results)
 - Sputum culture result should become negative [8–12]
 - Time to positivity in liquid medium (in days) should increase

These variables serve as indicators of a positive treatment response. If they deviate from expected patterns, it suggests that the patient's condition is not improving or may be worsening, indicating that the treatment is ineffective. When assessing new treatment regimens, drug candidates, vaccines, and similar interventions, if they work synergistically with the SoC, the improvements in the listed variables should occur more rapidly, resulting in a more pronounced slope of change over time.

A Good outcome (also known as a good treatment outcome) for TB is either bacteriological or clinical improvement, or both, at the end of treatment without any evidence of relapse within 6-24 months. Conversely, **a Bad outcome** is defined as the absence of bacteriological or clinical improvement, or both, by the end of TB treatment; early relapse; the necessity to prematurely terminate or switch to another TB treatment regimen; or death related to TB. Given the broad nature of these concepts, we have specifically defined what constitutes GOOD and BAD/POOR outcomes during the SMA-TB meeting in Oslo (June 2024), based on literature and our clinical experience.

SMA-TB considered Good or Bad/Poor responders based on the following criteria (Table 2):

- To measure the improvement or resolution of clinical signs and symptoms during and at the end of treatment, use TB score. The minimum value of the TB score is 0 and maximum 13. Higher scores mean a worse prognosis. Differences between each intervention arm and control group should be analysed, based on reaching the 50% or 75% improvement in TB Score values compared to baseline by weeks 8 and 24, respectively. The TB Score has been

described to be useful to monitor good response to TB treatment, regardless of HIV status [2,3].

- To measure the improvement in Health-related Quality of Life (HQoL) by comparing baseline measures with those taken during the therapy, use the SGRQ. The SGRQ total score ranges from 0 (best) to 100 (worst), with scores up to 7 considered to be within the healthy range. Improvement will be considered as achieving a score within the healthy range by weeks 8 and 24. Differences between each intervention arm and control group should be analysed.
- To measure the improvement or resolution of radiological signs during and at the end of treatment, use the Activity component of the RUTI TB Evolution Score [7]. Baseline chest X-ray (CXR) serves as the comparator against subsequent CXR images taken throughout TB therapy. The RTBES evaluates the findings and signs observed in the CXR, where the maximum value of the activity component being 38. The higher total scores indicate a worse prognosis. The difference in RTBES scores between each intervention arm and the control group should be analysed, reporting the achievement of minimum 50% or the 75% reduction of the Activity component of RTBES (by weeks 8 and 24, respectively).
- To measure the impact on the stable sputum culture conversion (SCC) rate and to facilitate the comparison with other clinical trials, use achieving stable SCC by week 8 to stratify the patients between fast and slow converters. Differences between each intervention arm and control group should be analysed.

Table 2. Criteria for stratifying patients as good or poor responders to treatment based on clinical, radiological, and microbiological outcomes

	Response at W8	Response at W24
Clinical outcomes	Good: $\geq 50\%$ sustainable* decrease in the TB Score vs BL; Poor: $< 50\%$ decrease in the TB Score vs BL	Good: $\geq 75\%$ decrease in the TB Score vs BL; Poor: $< 75\%$ decrease in the TB Score vs BL
	Good: Total SGRQ value ≤ 7 sustained*; POOR: Total SGRQ value > 7	GOOD: Total SGRQ value ≤ 7 ; POOR: Total SGRQ value > 7
Radiological outcome	Good: $\geq 50\%$ sustainable* decrease in the activity component of the RTBES score vs BL Poor: $< 50\%$ decrease in the activity component of the RTBES score vs BL	Good: $\geq 75\%$ decrease in the activity component of the RTBES score vs BL Poor: $< 75\%$ decrease in the activity component of the RTBES score vs BL
Microbiological outcome	Good: Fast responder, SCC \leq W8; Poor: Slow responder, SCC $>$ W8	N/A

SCC: Sputum Culture Conversion, SGRQ: Saint George's Respiratory Questionnaire; RTBES: Ruti TB Evolution Score; BL: Baseline, W8: week 8, W24: week 24, *Status "Good" sustained until week 24.

2. Assessment of Biomarkers

Assessment of Biomarkers for Reflecting Disease Status and Severity Over Time

First, one should plot the evolution of biomarkers throughout treatment at various time points.

Additionally, to assess the "disease status" partners should evaluate relation of their biomarkers/findings vs variables from the same time point (*e.g.*, *TGF- β level at baseline (BL) compared to RTBES score at BL, TGF- β level at week (W) 2 compared to RTBES score at W2*).

One should do this analysis for all time points available. If partners are unable to conduct experiments or analyses for all "Disease status" variables, please prioritize:

- Those working on pathogen factors should prioritise microbiological severity variables.
- Those working on host factors should prioritise clinical severity and radiological severity variables.

Evaluating the Ability of a Biomarker to Assess Treatment Response

The SMA-TB consortium agreed that the question to be answered would be “*Can xxx biomarker at BL level predict who will have a good or a bad response?*”). Good and Bad responders will be classified according to the criteria described above.

To achieve this, we will consider BL levels of the host/pathogen biomarker to determine if they can predict outcomes at W8 and W24. We will perform ROC analysis to evaluate the predictive performance of the model. By examining the ROC curve and the area under the curve (AUC), we can assess how well the model distinguishes between patients with different outcomes and select an appropriate classification threshold. *When the analysis is performed without splitting data into training and validation, the analysis will be considered only exploratory.*

For a result to be considered good, the AUC should be at least greater than 0,7. If any biomarker achieves this threshold, the cut-off for Sensitivity (S) and Specificity (E) should be calculated using the Youden index/cut-off value or by obtaining the values that yield the highest S and E in the software. If the achieved $S > 70\%$ and $E > 80\%$, then verify if the results for that specific biomarker meet the Target Product Profile defined by the WHO (Tables 4, 5, and 6) in the “Target product profiles for tests for tuberculosis treatment monitoring and optimization” document.

General remarks:

- All analysis should be performed considering data such as biological sex and RCT clinical site or at least country. All results should be stratified by biological sex, in case there are no differences, it can be mentioned as a text in the publication to make a statement.
- Use non-parametric tests.
- To perform correlation analysis: include all time points together. Use Spearman test for correlation.

3. References

1. Arias L, Otworld K, Waja Z, Tukvadze N, Korinteli T, Moloantoa T, et al. SMA-TB: study protocol for the phase 2b randomized double-blind, placebo-controlled trial to estimate the potential efficacy and safety of two repurposed drugs, acetylsalicylic acid and ibuprofen, for use as adjunct therapy added to, and compared with, the standard WHO recommended TB regimen. *Trials* [Internet]. 2023 Dec 1 [cited 2025 Apr 2];24(1):1–16. Available from: <https://trialsjournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13063-023-07448-0>
2. Wejse C, Gustafson P, Nielsen J, Gomes VF, Aaby P, Andersen PL, et al. TBscore: Signs and symptoms from tuberculosis patients in a low-resource setting have predictive value and may be used to assess clinical course. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00365540701558698> [Internet]. 2009 [cited 2023 Jul 13];40(2):111–20. Available from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00365540701558698>
3. Rudolf F. The Bandim TBscore – reliability, further development, and evaluation of potential uses. *Glob Health Action* [Internet]. 2014 [cited 2024 Aug 7];7(1):24303. Available from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.3402/gha.v7.24303>
4. Pasipanodya JG, Miller TL, Vecino M, Munguia G, Bae S, Drewyer G, et al. Using the St. George Respiratory Questionnaire to ascertain health quality in persons with treated pulmonary tuberculosis. *Chest* [Internet]. 2007 Nov 1 [cited 2023 Jul 13];132(5):1591–8. Available from: <http://journal.chestnet.org/article/S0012369215512762/fulltext>
5. Kissling M, Fritschi N, Baumann P, Buettcher M, Bonhoeffer J, Naranbhai V, et al. Monocyte, Lymphocyte and Neutrophil Ratios - Easy-to-Use Biomarkers for the Diagnosis of Pediatric Tuberculosis. *Pediatr Infect Dis J* [Internet]. 2023 Jun 1 [cited 2023 Jul 19];42(6):520–7. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36977187/>
6. Buttle TS, Hummerstone CY, Billahalli T, Ward RJB, Barnes KE, Marshall NJ, et al. The monocyte-to-lymphocyte ratio: Sex-specific differences in the tuberculosis disease spectrum, diagnostic indices and defining normal ranges. *PLoS One* [Internet]. 2021 Aug 1 [cited 2023 Jul 19];16(8):e0247745. Available from: <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0247745>
7. Cuadras P, Rafart G, Català M, Arias L, Pérez R, Martinson N, et al. RTBES Radiological Index for Quantitative Assessment of Tuberculosis Evolution: Development and Validation. *medRxiv* [Internet]. 2025 Feb 18 [cited 2025 Apr 2];2025.02.14.25322286. Available from: <https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2025.02.14.25322286v1>
8. Rockwood N, du Bruyn E, Morris T, Wilkinson RJ. Assessment of treatment response in tuberculosis. Vol. 10, *Expert Review of Respiratory Medicine*. Taylor and Francis Ltd.; 2016. p. 643–54.
9. World Health Organization. WHO consolidated guidelines on tuberculosis Module 1: Prevention Infection prevention and control. 2020.
10. Ramarokoto H, Randriamiharisoa H, Rakotoarisaonina A, Rasolovavalona T, Rasolofo V, Chanteau S, et al. Bacteriological follow-up of tuberculosis treatment: a comparative study of smear microscopy and culture results at the second month of treatment.
11. Rieder HL. Sputum smear conversion during directly observed treatment for tuberculosis. *Tubercle and Lung Disease*. 1996 Apr 1;77(2):124–9.
12. Kurbatova E V., Cegielski JP, Lienhardt C, Akksilp R, Bayona J, Becerra MC, et al. Sputum culture conversion as a prognostic marker for end-of-treatment outcome in patients with multidrug-resistant tuberculosis: a secondary analysis of data from two observational cohort studies. *Lancet Respir Med* [Internet]. 2015 Feb 26 [cited 2024 Aug 7];3(3):201–9. Available from: <https://europepmc.org/articles/PMC4401426>

